

Construction and Standardization of 'RTE Act Awareness Scale' for Upper Primary School Teachers

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Abstract

The present study is an effort to construct and standardize a self-made research tool named 'RTE Act Awareness Scale' to find out the awareness of Upper Primary school teachers towards the provisions of RTE Act 2009. The researcher identified total 8 dimensions of RTE Act to prepare the draft of research tool. A total of 56 items were selected for pre-tryout draft after the clearance of three experts. Against each item there were two responses as 'Yes' and 'No'. The draft was administered among 150 upper primary school teachers of 20 schools of Sambhal district in Uttar Pradesh for pre try out. The schools were selected by purposive sampling. After item analysis of pre try out by experts a total of 46 items out of 56 items, were selected for final draft of RTE Act Awareness Scale. Out of 46 items, 26 items were positive and 20 were negative. The reliability of the test was found as 0.88 by spearman Brown formula of reliability coefficient.

Keywords: RTE Act 2009, Awareness, upper primary schools, construction, standardization

Introduction:-

Education is a tool to change the society. Education to all may be a solution to empower the whole society and generations. The educational facilities must be reached to every door if we want to educate every citizen of our country. Firstly, in India Maharaja Sayaji Rao Gayakwad, ruler of Baroda state made a successful effort to provide the free education to children. After that, during British rule Gopal Krishnan Gokhale presented a Bill to have a demand for free and compulsory education before British rule in 1910-1911, but failed. Again in 1937 Mahatma Gandhi served an idea for free and compulsory education before 'Rashtriya Shiksha Parishad' but Parishad rejected the proposal due to lack of economic resources. The issue to Free and Compulsory Education also rose toward the constitution assembly but the Assembly put this issue under 'Directive Principles of State Policy' under article 45, not in the category of fundamental rights. The Supreme Court judgment in the case of Unnikrishnan J.P. vs. State of Andhra Pradesh and others (SC. 2178, 1993) makes elementary education a fundamental right and states that; "The right of life is incomplete without education and it is a supreme duty of state to provide free and compulsory education for the age group 6-14 years." In 2002 Indian parliament passed a constitutional amendment and a new sub article in article 21 as article 21A was included. So the issue of free and compulsory education took a form of fundamental right of elementary education to the age group 6-14 years.

The Right of Children to Free and Compulsory Education (RTE) Act 2009 passed by the Indian parliament mandates free and compulsory education of all children of 6-14 years age until they complete elementary education in a neighborhood school. The RTE Act 2009 shall make an arrangement to free and compulsory education for every child of India. To take elementary education facilities, is the fundamental

right of every child and the state is directly responsible to provide elementary education infrastructure for children education to the age group of 6-14 years. There some silent features of RTE Act 2009.

- State shall provide free and compulsory elementary education to every child of 6 to 14 years of age group in prescribed manner.
- Every private school shall admit 25 % of children of weaker section for free elementary education.
- Mental and physical harassment of child will be banned.
- Curriculum should be in mother tongue of child and in child centered manner.
- No child will be held back in any class till completion his/ her elementary education.
- School Management Committee will be responsible to prepare school development plan.
- State shall provide academic and physical infrastructure for every school.

If we want good implementation of RTE Act 2009 and want that it would be Magna Carta of Indian Elementary Education, it is desirable that every teacher should have awareness of the provisions of RTE Act 2009. In this context, present study is an attempt to construct 'RTE Act Awareness Scale'.

Development of Scale

If we bear responsibility to implement any scheme, it will be must to have awareness about that. Here, the researcher wants to know the awareness of upper primary school teachers towards the provisions of RTE Act 2009.

Construction of RTE Act Awareness Scale

A draft of RTE Act Awareness Scale to measure the awareness towards the provisions of RTE Act 2009, among the teachers of district Sambhal was developed to check the awareness of the awareness of upper primary school teachers.

I. Preparation of the Draft of RTE Act Awareness Scale

The research literature and RTE Act 2009 has been consulted and studied thoroughly for construction of RTE Act Awareness Scale.

From the study of RTE Act 2009 and related literature following dimensions for development of RTE Act Awareness have been found out which were taken for the construction of the present RTE Awareness Scale.

- i. Introduction of RTE Act 2009.
- ii. Duties of Appropriate government, local authority and parents.
- iii. Responsibilities of school and teachers.
- iv. School Management Committee.
- v. Curriculum and completion of elementary education.
- vi. Protection of child rights.
- vii. Principal formation authority.
- viii. Norms and standards for a school.

Both, positive and negative statements/ items were taken. Against each item, there are two responses- 'Yes' and 'No'. The option with which the subject agrees is to be ticked. Necessary editing of the statements has been done by the researcher. All the statements were shown to the supervisor and experts for suggestions and finally some items were modified and some of them were dropped. A total 56 items were selected, out of which 33 statements were

positive and 28 statements were negative. All the items were arranged randomly and final draft was prepared. The distribution of the selected items of the draft 'RTE Act Awareness Scale' is given in the table no. 1.

S.N.	Dimensions of the Draft	Positive items	Negative items	No. of Positive items	No. of negative items	Total
1.	Introduction of RTE Act 2009	1,2,5,6,	3,4,7,8,9	04	05	09
2.	Duties of Appropriate government, local authority and parents	10,12,13, 14,16,18	11,15,17,19	06	04	10
3.	Responsibilities of school and teachers	21,24,25,26, 28,48,49	20,22,23,27, 29	07	05	12
4.	School management committee	43,44,45,46	42	04	01	05
5.	Curriculum and completion of elementary education	38,40	39,41	02	02	04
6.	Protection of child rights	33,34,35,36, 37	00	05	00	05
7.	Principle formation authority	00	47,31,32	00	03	03
8.	Norms and standards for a school	50,51,52,53, 55	30, 54, 56	05	03	08
G. Total				33	23	56

Table- 1

II. Tryout of the draft of RTE Act Awareness Scale

For the purpose of the tryout, the draft of RTE Act Awareness Scale was administered on 120 upper primary school teachers of district Sambhal, in Uttar Pradesh. The school teachers for tryout were selected through purposive sampling. Oral instructions were also provided where ever it was necessary. Obstacles were also noted during the tryout of RTE Act Awareness Scale.

III. Item analysis

The researcher decided to select 46 items on the basis of experts' advice and suggestions for the final draft of 'RTE Act Awareness Scale'. To select these 46 items, researcher gave proper weightage to both positive and negative items according the need of dimensions. The distribution of selected items are shown in the table no. 6

S.N.	Dimensions of the Draft	Positive items	Negative items	No. of Positive items	No. of negative items	Total
1.	Introduction of RTE Act 2009	2,5,6,	1,3,9	03	03	06
2.	Duties of Appropriate government, local authority and parents	10,12,14, 16,18	11,15,19	05	03	08
3.	Responsibilities of school and teachers	21,24,28,48, 49	20,22,23,27, 29	05	05	10

4.	School management committee	44	43	01	01	02
5.	Curriculum and completion of elementary education	40,41	39,38	02	02	04
6.	Protection of child rights	33,36,37	34,35	03	02	05
7.	Principle formation authority	32,47	31	02	01	03
8.	Norms and standards for a school	50,51,52,53,55	30, 54, 56	05	03	08
G. Total				26	20	46

Table no. 6

IV. Jumbling in the final selected items for research tool

After selection the final draft through expert's item analysis, Items were mixed by jumbling them. After jumbling the items are placed in the following table no. 7

S.N.	Dimensions of the Draft	Positive items	Negative items	No. of Positive items	No. of negative items	Total
1.	Introduction of RTE Act 2009	3,7,11	1,5,9	03	03	06
2.	Duties of Appropriate government, local authority and parents	2,6,15,19,23	13,17,20	05	03	08
3.	Responsibilities of school and teachers	10,14,18,21,29	4,8,12,16,24	05	05	10
4.	School management committee	26	28	01	01	02
5.	Curriculum and completion of elementary education	30,34	32,36	02	02	04
6.	Protection of child rights	42,46,22	40,43	03	02	05
7.	Principle formation authority	25,38	27	02	01	03
8.	Norms and standards for a school	33,37,41,44,45	31,35,39	05	03	08
G. Total				26	20	46

Table no. 7

V. Scoring

The scoring key for positive and negative statements against two responses were determined as given in the table 3.13

Nature of items	'Yes' Aware	'No' Non- Aware
Positive	1	0
Negative	0	1

Table no.8

VI. Validity

To determine the validity of 'RTE Act Awareness Scale' the researcher sent the RTE Act Awareness Scale to a number of experts seeking judgment regarding the coverage of construct and it was found satisfactory.

VII. Reliability

To seeking the reliability of RTE Act Awareness, the test was divided into two equal parts as first half and second half by split half method. Then the coefficient of correlation between these two parts of test was calculated using the formula of product moment coefficient of correlation (Pearson method) which calculates the reliability of half test and reliability of half test was found **0.7973**. The coefficient of reliability of the whole test was estimated by using Spearman-Brown formula and it was found **0.88**

Conclusion

Finally, 46 items were selected out of 56 items. These 46 items include both negative and positive items. The reliability of the present tool was found 0.88, which was highly satisfactory. Thus, the 'RTE Act Awareness Scale' has been prepared for final administration.

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